

A Contribution To the General Field Theory

1. Introduction

This work is a result (1983-2020) of thirty-seven years of deliberations. It is based solely on circumstantial evidence, assumptions and guesses. None of the described elements of this work has been proven either theoretically or experimentally. Although a lot of experiments that could confirm circumstantial evidence could be carried out, the lack of funds prevented me from doing the same. After many years, I thought that it was worth writing own and publishing the accumulation of so many circumstantial evidence on the same subject in hope of their contribution to better knowledge of the world, although I think that the probability of correctness of the assumptions is extremely low.

2. Assumptions:

a) "God does not play dice"

b) Let us assume that there is a particle, which is a source of the magnetic and electric field, in which H and E intensity vectors facing each other at the angle of $\alpha=90^\circ$.

$$\int \bar{H} dt \times \int \bar{E} dt = \int \bar{G} dt$$
$$\int \bar{H} dt * \int \bar{E} dt * \sin \alpha = \int \bar{G} dt$$
$$\sin \alpha = \sin 90^\circ = 1$$

To simplify and put it in a less elegant manner:

$$\frac{A}{m^2} * \frac{V}{s} = G$$

$$\frac{W}{m^2} = G$$

$$G = \frac{J}{m^2 * s}$$

$$G = \frac{N * m}{m^2 * s}$$

$$G = \frac{kg * m^2}{m^2 * s^3}$$

$$G = \frac{kg}{s^3}$$

$$G = \frac{\rho * m^3}{s^3}$$

$$G = \rho c^3 \quad (\text{gravitational field intensity})$$

c) Let us assume that the particle described in b) is as follows:

Let us refer to it as Kuszon (K).

d) Let us assume that K particle will merge with other K particle by the force of gravity at a small distance.

I. In this case, the image will be as follows:

The particle reminds that of a familiar photon. The gravitational field vectors cancel each other. The particle has a magnetic and electric field resultant vector. By rotating, the photon creates something that can be observed as an electromagnetic wave. It is interesting why the photon track is curved near a star, for example, given that it does not have any mass. It is only the zero vector that has a mass.

Source: Wikipedia

II. Other position of K particles in relation to each other may be as follows:

This position of K particles in relation to each other resembles that of an electron. It has a mass, an electric field vector and, what is new, a magnetic field vector. Why does an electron, in a classic situation, reacts to the magnetic field, if it does not have anything in common with magnetism? The force of an electron in the magnetic and electric field is, as we know, shifted by 90° . The electric and magnetic field vectors are also shifted by 90° as shown in the figure above.

III. Another position of K particles in relation to each other may be as follows:

This position of K particles resembles a neutrino. It has a zero mass and zero electric field. Therefore, the matter force is very weak. However, the particle has a magnetic field.

3. If scientists are brave enough to present the string theory, time travel or explain the presence of black matter in other parallel worlds, even if those are supported with a mathematic propaganda, I think that my hypotheses are less brave, though equally unbelievable.

4. Suggested experiments and other:

- a) Detecting the number of electrons actually flowing through a circuit consisting of a light source in order to prove that electrons change into photons.
- b) We put a large boulder or a block of steel (weighing several tons or more) on accurate scales. After connecting the scales to a very large electric or magnetic field, we observe, whether, the weight changes in order to prove that gravitational vectors will assume positions, in which the resultant will be lower downward.
- c) In a radio aerial an electron changes into a photon as a result of resonance in the LC circuit.
- d) The particle explains, why there are so many neutrinos in the world.
- e) If a neutrino has a zero mass, it may, however, build black matter as a result of reversed vectors.
- f) Young's interference experiment involves a hole and not a wave.
- g) X-radiation or gamma radiation are effects of photons rotating around their axis even faster as a result of, for example, the energy of explosion of a supernova.